

Rutor Digisky aerial 2021

Processing Report

07 May 2024

Survey Data

Fig. 1. Camera locations and image overlap.

Number of images:	1,030	Camera stations:	997
Flying altitude:	804 m	Tie points:	505,977
Ground resolution:	6.27 cm/pix	Projections:	3,425,721
Coverage area:	34.8 km ²	Reprojection error:	0.586 pix

Camera Model	Resolution	Focal Length	Pixel Size	Precalibrated
iXM-RS150F, Rodenstoc...	14204 x 10652	50 mm	3.76 x 3.76 μm	No

Table 1. Cameras.

Camera Calibration

Fig. 2. Image residuals for iXM-RS150F, Rodenstock RS-50mm/Aerial (50mm).

iXM-RS150F, Rodenstock RS-50mm/Aerial (50mm)

1014 images

Type	Resolution	Focal Length	Pixel Size
Frame	14204 x 10652	50 mm	3.76 x 3.76 μm

	Value	Error	F	Cx	Cy	B1	B2	K1	K2	K3	K4	P1	P2
F	13740.6	0.1	1.00	-0.31	-0.67	0.05	-0.06	-0.06	0.06	-0.05	0.04	-0.01	-0.01
Cx	58.0346	0.013		1.00	0.20	-0.05	0.08	-0.00	0.00	-0.00	0.01	0.76	-0.01
Cy	-7.72876	0.014			1.00	-0.08	0.02	0.00	-0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.57
B1	0.217977	0.0036				1.00	-0.00	0.02	-0.02	0.02	-0.02	0.01	0.01
B2	-0.90192	0.0036					1.00	0.00	-0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.02
K1	-0.00483364	1.4e-05						1.00	-0.98	0.93	-0.89	-0.01	-0.00
K2	0.0106506	0.00013							1.00	-0.99	0.96	0.01	-0.01
K3	0.0479761	0.00047								1.00	-0.99	-0.01	0.01
K4	-0.111596	0.00058									1.00	0.01	-0.00
P1	1.54472e-05	2.9e-07										1.00	-0.00
P2	9.69403e-05	2.6e-07											1.00

Table 2. Calibration coefficients and correlation matrix.

Ground Control Points

Fig. 3. GCP locations and error estimates.

Z error is represented by ellipse color. X,Y errors are represented by ellipse shape.

Estimated GCP locations are marked with a dot or crossing.

Count	X error (cm)	Y error (cm)	Z error (cm)	XY error (cm)	Total (cm)
9	3.44737	3.2796	6.15283	4.75816	7.77801

Table 3. Control points RMSE.

X - Easting, Y - Northing, Z - Altitude.

Count	X error (cm)	Y error (cm)	Z error (cm)	XY error (cm)	Total (cm)
4	7.59541	1.6699	11.7984	7.77681	14.1309

Table 4. Check points RMSE.

X - Easting, Y - Northing, Z - Altitude.

Label	X error (cm)	Y error (cm)	Z error (cm)	Total (cm)	Image (pix)
GCP07	0.376596	2.63743	1.19937	2.92171	0.336 (11)
GCP04	-2.66182	4.03174	-7.0668	8.56037	0.309 (32)
GCP02	-1.3843	0.683368	3.88985	4.185	0.348 (21)
GCP07	5.41751	1.89144	1.57074	5.9493	1.067 (8)
GCP03	-1.94006	-0.826232	2.51957	3.28554	0.316 (20)
GCP01	0.32524	1.57072	9.46181	9.59681	0.331 (29)
GCP06	-2.62369	-2.45089	0.962234	3.71706	0.231 (17)
GCP05	-3.98059	-7.76768	0.672345	8.75409	0.280 (16)
GCP04	6.47053	0.2299	-13.2094	14.7108	2.227 (10)
Total	3.44737	3.2796	6.15283	7.77801	0.667

Table 5. Control points.
X - Easting, Y - Northing, Z - Altitude.

Label	X error (cm)	Y error (cm)	Z error (cm)	Total (cm)	Image (pix)
CP03	-3.9849	1.78171	-11.2822	12.0972	0.248 (21)
CP04	-2.00467	-2.45014	0.929865	3.29948	0.430 (6)
CP01	-4.0963	-0.0558166	17.5501	18.0219	0.311 (5)
CP02	-13.9314	-1.40479	10.9844	17.7964	0.322 (8)
Total	7.59541	1.6699	11.7984	14.1309	0.305

Table 6. Check points.
X - Easting, Y - Northing, Z - Altitude.

Digital Elevation Model

Fig. 4. Reconstructed digital elevation model.

Resolution: 12.5 cm/pix
Point density: 63.6 points/m²

Processing Parameters

General

Cameras	1014
Aligned cameras	997
Markers	13
Coordinate system	RDN2008 / UTM zone 32N (N-E) (EPSG::6707)
Rotation angles	Yaw, Pitch, Roll

Tie Points

Points	505,977 of 587,355
RMS reprojection error	0.105898 (0.586334 pix)
Max reprojection error	0.509266 (43.2814 pix)
Mean key point size	4.98914 pix
Point colors	3 bands, uint8
Key points	No
Average tie point multiplicity	7.45368

Alignment parameters

Accuracy	Medium
Generic preselection	Yes
Reference preselection	No
Key point limit	40,000
Key point limit per Mpx	1,000
Tie point limit	4,000
Exclude stationary tie points	No
Guided image matching	No
Adaptive camera model fitting	No
Matching time	1 hours 11 minutes
Matching memory usage	1.08 GB
Alignment time	4 minutes 30 seconds
Alignment memory usage	439.61 MB

Optimization parameters

Parameters	f, b1, b2, cx, cy, k1-k4, p1, p2
Adaptive camera model fitting	No
Optimization time	9 seconds
Date created	2021:10:30 10:20:40
Software version	1.7.4.13028
File size	80.19 MB

Depth Maps

Count	1033
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Depth maps generation parameters

Quality	High
Filtering mode	Mild
Max neighbors	40
Processing time	14 hours 37 minutes
Memory usage	56.47 GB
Date created	2021:11:20 08:08:36
Software version	1.7.4.13028
File size	44.83 GB

Point Cloud

Points	3,342,984,543
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Point attributes

Color	3 bands, uint8
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Normal	
Confidence	1 - 80
Point classes	
Created (never classified)	3,342,984,543
Depth maps generation parameters	
Quality	High
Filtering mode	Mild
Max neighbors	40
Processing time	14 hours 37 minutes
Memory usage	56.47 GB
Point cloud generation parameters	
Processing time	1 days 2 hours
Memory usage	54.45 GB
Date created	2023:06:20 15:39:22
Software version	1.8.3.14331
File size	46.60 GB
DEM	
Size	76,675 x 78,207
Coordinate system	RDN2008 / UTM zone 32N (N-E) (EPSG::6707)
Reconstruction parameters	
Source data	Point cloud
Interpolation	Enabled
Processing time	48 minutes 30 seconds
Memory usage	380.62 MB
Date created	2023:06:21 08:11:46
Software version	1.8.3.14331
File size	7.69 GB
Orthomosaic	
Size	125,215 x 135,015
Coordinate system	RDN2008 / UTM zone 32N (N-E) (EPSG::6707)
Colors	3 bands, uint8
Reconstruction parameters	
Blending mode	Mosaic
Surface	DEM
Enable hole filling	Yes
Enable ghosting filter	No
Processing time	10 hours 39 minutes
Memory usage	5.97 GB
Date created	2023:06:21 17:55:54
Software version	1.8.3.14331
File size	193.27 GB
System	
Software name	Agisoft Metashape Professional
Software version	2.0.3 build 16960
OS	Windows 64 bit
RAM	63.68 GB
CPU	Intel(R) Core(TM) i9-9900X CPU @ 3.50GHz
GPU(s)	Quadro RTX 4000